

The Social Consequences of the First Industrial Revolution

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I. Introduction

The radical transformation of the status quo between 1760 and 1840, known as the First Industrial Revolution, was driven by the widespread adoption of steel and iron, as well as the extensive use of energy sources and locomotion technologies such as coal and the steam engine. In Great Britain, where coal was an abundant and inexpensive energy source and labor relatively costly, both inventors and investors were attracted by the possibility of generating profits through the creation of coal-powered machines that reduced dependence on human labor. This incentive led to the widespread adoption of inventions such as James Watt's steam engine and Edmund Cartwright's power loom (Cartwright, 2023).

Steam power enabled machines such as the power loom to replace costly skilled labor, resulting in a massive increase in textile production. Additionally, steam was used as a power source for trains and ships, and in agriculture, devices such as the threshing machine replaced human labor. Mechanized factories displaced cottage industries and accelerated urbanization, leading to the development of entire cities around major coal deposits. This economic transformation also influenced social structures, creating new jobs and increasing urban demand for manufactured goods, thereby fueling the process of industrialization (Britannica, 2024).

The social and cultural consequences of the First Industrial Revolution were reflected in literary works of the Georgian and Victorian periods, such as the novels of Charles Dickens—particularly *Oliver Twist* and *Great Expectations*—as well as *The Picture of Dorian Gray* by Oscar Wilde. These works highlight the precariousness and misery of the time, illustrating the growing divide between capitalists and proletarians as a result of exploitation, urban overcrowding, and unequal wealth distribution.

Given this context, it is important to ask whether the quality of life of the average worker was better or worse before the Industrial Revolution. After all, ancient and medieval history included systems such as slavery, serfdom, and the controversial *droit du seigneur*. By abolishing these systems and giving way to industrialization, can it truly be said that human quality of life improved?

II. Working Conditions

Before the Industrial Revolution, skilled artisans produced most of Europe's manufactured goods. Their work was governed by the traditions of their craft and the limits of available resources. The primary sources of energy were human and animal labor, as well as water wheels.

With the rise of mechanized production, a faster and more demanding work rhythm was established. In workplaces such as coal mines, working hours were extremely long and conditions generally dangerous. Workers had little bargaining power, which contributed to persistently poor labor conditions, and they often lived in deplorable circumstances.

According to an anthropometric study by Blum and McLaughlin (2019), which examines living standards and inequality during the Industrial Revolution, health and nutritional standards—proxied by average height—declined during industrialization. Urbanization, poor sanitation and hygiene, inadequate housing, and heavy workloads placed pressure on physical development, often resulting in stunted growth. Moreover, the distance from food production centers and high transaction costs led to relatively high food prices in urban areas, resulting in poor nutrition. Horrell and Oxley (cited in Blum & McLaughlin, 2019) found clear evidence of stunting in children born in the 1830s compared to modern WHO growth standards.

Although relatively little is known about inequality trends during this period, rapid industrialization and structural change undoubtedly altered social distributions. Monetary indicators suggest that in the United Kingdom, wealth and income disparities widened during the early stages of industrialization. Allen (2019) found that a larger share of income accrued to the top decile and that the Gini coefficient increased from 0.54 (1668/1759) to 0.60 (1798). These findings imply that early industrialization disproportionately benefited capital over other factors of production (Blum & McLaughlin, 2019).

III. Child Labor

During the Industrial Revolution, children were widely employed in factories, mines, and agriculture. They often worked 12-hour shifts, just like adults, and children as young as five received minimal pay for tasks such as crawling under dangerous machinery, transporting coal through narrow mine shafts, or working in agricultural groups.

In many cases, children's roles were clearly defined, meaning child labor was not merely supplementary to adult labor. Education was frequently replaced by work, a choice often made by parents to supplement insufficient household income (Cartwright, 2023).

A testimony cited in Shelley (2016) states:

“I am 12 years old. I started working in the mines about seven and a half years ago opening doors. I had a candle and a fire beside me for light... I worked 12 hours a day and earned 6

pence a day... When I got paid, I took the money home to my mother... Once I fell asleep and was severely beaten by a driver.” (Own translation)

Similarly, as illustrated in *Oliver Twist*, orphans worked while being subjected to physical and emotional abuse by their caregivers.

However, it would be misleading to assume that child labor did not exist prior to industrialization. In traditional handicraft industries, children contributed to family production processes—for example, washing wool so their mothers could spin it and fathers could weave it. Likewise, children worked in small family businesses such as basket-making, blacksmithing, and pottery.

Artisans also took on apprentices, who were provided with food and lodging and trained in a specific trade. In return, they worked without pay and were often required to pay an initial fee for contracts lasting several years (Cartwright, 2023).

What distinguished the Industrial Revolution from earlier systems was the massive increase in production, which stimulated consumption and led to the hiring of more labor under exhausting conditions in overcrowded factories with inadequate working environments. Additionally, industries such as coal mining created highly unsanitary workplaces for both children and adults.

IV. Real Wages

A fundamental metric for evaluating changes in quality of life during the Industrial Revolution is the concept of the standard of living. While ideally this would be linked to happiness—a subjective aspect of human experience—its quantitative measurement is inherently problematic. Economists therefore rely on monetary indicators such as real wages as proxies.

According to Nardinelli, Lindert and Williamson (1983) produced new estimates of real wages in England from 1755 to 1851. Their findings showed slow growth between 1781 and 1819, followed by rapid increases thereafter. Real wages doubled between 1819 and 1851.

However, other economists challenged these optimistic findings. Feinstein’s alternative series suggested much slower growth. Additionally, while wages were higher in cities, so were rents, and overall living conditions were often worse. Brown argued that higher urban wages partly compensated for poor working and living conditions.

Estimates by Crafts indicate that British per capita income rose from approximately \$400 in 1760 to \$800 in 1860, with slow growth before 1830 and faster growth afterward.

These estimates suggest a moderately optimistic long-term outlook but allow for pessimistic conclusions in shorter periods. Many economic historians agree that income inequality increased between 1790 and 1840, and when accounting for unemployment, poor harvests, war, pollution, and urban overcrowding, modest income growth may have coincided with declining living standards for the working class.

Additional evidence supports gradual improvement. Consumption per capita rose only slightly between 1760 and 1820 but increased rapidly afterward. Life expectancy rose from 35 to 40 years between 1781 and 1851—a modest but significant improvement for the time.

In summary, while the Industrial Revolution ultimately increased real wages, these gains materialized mainly in the mid-19th century. Early benefits were offset by rapid population growth and harsh working conditions.

V. Conclusion

The Industrial Revolution was a period of profound technological and economic transformation that brought significant advancements alongside substantial challenges. It was characterized by harsh labor conditions, public health issues, and rising social inequality.

These hardships laid the foundation for modern labor protections, as responses to industrial abuses led to the emergence of labor regulations and unions aimed at protecting workers, limiting child labor, and reducing working hours.

Although real incomes increased slightly during the early Industrial Revolution, it was the technological innovations of this period that triggered the explosive economic growth of the 19th century, which has continued to expand to the present day. These advancements enabled mass production and improved material living conditions across social classes.

Nevertheless, material wealth does not necessarily translate into happiness, raising important questions about the human and social costs of these historical transformations.

VI. References

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